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Frustration recognition from speech during game interaction using wide residual networks

Meishu SONG^{1*}, Adria MALLOL-RAGOLTA¹, Emilia PARADA-CABALEIRO¹,
Zijiang YANG¹, Shuo LIU¹, Zhao REN¹, Ziping ZHAO³, and Björn W.
SCHULLER^{1,2}

1. *Chair of Embedded Intelligence for Health Care and Wellbeing, University of Augsburg, Germany*

2. *GLAM - Group on Language, Audio, & Music, Imperial College London, the UK*

3. *Department of Computer Science, Tianjin Normal University, China*

* **Corresponding author:** meishu.song@informatik.uni-augsburg.de

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Abstract Background Although frustration is a common emotional reaction during playing games, an excessive level of frustration can harm users' experiences, discouraging them from undertaking further game interactions. The automatic detection of players' frustration enables the development of adaptive systems, which through a real-time difficulty adjustment, would adapt the game to the user's specific needs; thus, maximising players experience and guaranteeing the game success. To this end, we present our speech-based approach for the automatic detection of frustration during game interactions, a specific task still under-explored in research. **Method** The experiments were performed on the Multimodal Game Frustration Database (MGFD), an audiovisual dataset—collected within the Wizard-of-Oz framework—specially tailored to investigate verbal and facial expressions of frustration during game interactions. We explored the performance of a variety of acoustic feature sets, including Mel-Spectrograms and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), as well as the low dimensional knowledge-based acoustic feature set eGeMAPS. Due to the always increasing improvements achieved by the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in speech recognition tasks, unlike the MGFD baseline—based on Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier—in the present work we take into consideration typically used CNNs, including ResNets, VGG, and AlexNet. Furthermore, given the still open debate on the shallow vs deep networks suitability, we also examine the

performance of two of the latest deep CNNs, i. e., WideResNets and EfficientNet. **Results** Our best result, achieved with WideResNets and Mel-Spectrogram features, increases the system performance from 58.8 % Unweighted Average Recall (UAR) to 93.1 % UAR for speech-based automatic frustration recognition.

Keywords Frustration Recognition; WideResNets; Machine Learning

1 Introduction

Emotion-related theories define frustration as “the occurrence of an obstacle that prevents the satisfaction of a need”^[1], an emotional state that has been studied since the early years of the 20th century^[1] and which is of special interest in the field of human behaviour analysis. Since frustration is a common reaction triggered during playing games^[2], it is also studied within the human-game interaction paradigm. In this context, frustration is a negative emotional state that occurs in goal-oriented games, when a feeling of dissatisfaction arises from a player’s unfulfilled needs^[3]. Experiencing frustration while interacting with games also triggers a variety of negative emotional responses, such as acute stress, sadness, or rage, to name a few. These emotions impact a users’ opinion of the playing experience, usually negatively influencing their evaluation and therefore reducing the acceptance of the game itself^[4]. In this regard, recent developments in computer games analysis have as a main goal to improve the User Experience(UX)^[5] through the elicitation, detection, and modelling of players’ emotions while gaming. Indeed, frustration has been identified as a common emotional reaction during game interactions^[6] that negatively impacts the UX^[5]. Hence, the development of technology able to effectively recognise and reduce users’ frustration while playing games is expected as highly beneficial to improve user experience.

Although affective computing^[7] technologies have been already applied in the field of gaming research^[5], the automatic analysis of frustration during playing games is still an underdeveloped area of investigation. Indeed, due to the difficulties linked to the collection of suitable and realistic databases^[8], existing datasets, adequate for the study of frustration during game interactions, are still rare. One exception is the Multimodal Game Frustration Database(MGFD)^[9], which presents spontaneous players’ interactions during playing “Crazy Trophy”, a voice-controlled game in which frustration was elicited by creating usability problems. Both, users’ spoken and facial expressions, were recorded, and the interactions were labelled in terms of presence or absence of frustration. An initial work on the MGFD presented a baseline based on Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent

Neural Network (LSTM-RNN), applying Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) acoustic features, for the automatic detection of frustration/non-frustration states from users' facial expressions and speech^[9].

Beyond SVM and LSTM-RNN, which have been successfully employed in speech analysis tasks^[10], other neural network techniques such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have also shown promising results for such tasks^[11]; specifically, the research in^[12] obtained a higher performance with CNNs w. r. t. RNNs. Previous work has partially shown that CNNs are more suitable over LSTM-RNNs for the classifications of long sentences in a natural language processing task^[13]. Similarly, attention-based CNNs have also achieved better results than attention-based LSTM-RNNs for answer selection with an open domain question-answer selection dataset^[14]. These results might be due to the fact that while RNNs^[15] compute cyclic connections for the input features, CNNs use the invariance of deep convolutions to overcome the diversity of the speech signals and multi-layers enriched features^[16]. Considering this, we anticipate that the use of CNNs would achieve good performance on the recognition of users' frustration on the MFGD. Research on CNNs has led to a series of breakthroughs in machine learning tasks, leading to the exploration of 'very deep' models, which have become the today's state-of-the-art research^[17]. However, a 'degradation' problem might arise when deep networks start to converge, which would lead to a detriment in accuracy^[17]. For instance, Residual Networks (ResNets^[18]) have shown to efficiently scale up to hundreds of layers while maintaining an improving performance^[19]. Still, each fraction of percentage of improved accuracy usually costs nearly doubling the number of layers. Likewise, training very deep residual networks tends towards the problem of diminishing feature reuse. Further, the shared information among all blocks is limited and not enough to provide a sufficient contribution^[19]. To address this problem, WideResNets was designed, which randomly disables the residual blocks during training and widening residual blocks can perform superior to thin and deep counterparts^[19].

In this work, our goal is to overcome the drawbacks of a limited feature set and machine learning models as considered in the MFGD baseline, thus we extract a larger variety of audio feature sets w. r. t. those considered in the baseline paper, and apply state-of-the-art deep CNNs for the automatic identification of users' frustration during game interactions. We provide a comparison of a variety of CNNs, including: AlexNet, VGG, EfficientNet, ResNets, and WideResNets, as well as consider different feature sets: MFCCs, Mel-Spectrograms, and eGeMAPS. Likewise, we find the most efficient configuration for frustration recognition on the

MGFD.

2 Related work

Although the emotional database with a focus on frustration are rare^[9], the interest on modelling this emotion through computational means is clearly shown by the variety of database, introduced in the literature, which contain, in some extent, frustration. As far as audio content is concerned, the UTDrive database contains recordings collected in real conditions while driving in urban areas^{[20]. [21]}. In the ChIMP-Children’s Interactive Multimedia Project database, collected during children-computer interactions, verbal expressions of frustration are evaluated^[22]. Datasets annotated in terms of frustration are indeed relatively common in the literature, especially those containing also other emotional states. For instance, DEAP, the Dataset for Emotion Analysis using Physiological Signals^[23], which was recorded while subjects were watching musical videos, provides Electroencephalogram (EEG) and peripheral physiological signals. Similarly, FEEDB, the Database of Facial Expressions and Emotions^[24], contains synchronised facial colour videos and depth maps—both of them containing frustration and other emotional annotations. Finally, although the validity of acted emotions has been criticized^[25], audiovisual datasets containing acted expressions of frustration, such as in IEMOCAP, the Interactive EMOTional dyadic motion CAPture database^[26], or the Chen-Huang database^[27], frustration has also been presented. All in all, despite the interest on frustration shown by existing emotional database, the lack of corpus focusing on this emotion has limited the development of systems able to automatically recognise user’ frustration.

Concerning recent advance in neural networks based research, it has been shown that properly widening the residual blocks instead of increasing the depth of residual blocks, can lead to much more effective residual networks; thus, improving the performance^[28]. Recent research on image-based food recognition^[29] has shown that wide residual blocks with sliced convolution can successfully capture specific information, leading indeed to a better performance w.r.t. existing approaches. On the ILSVRC12 image classification task, i. e., the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge, wide residual networks with smaller depth showed comparable accuracy to that achieved by less wide and more deep ResNets^[30]. Such ‘WideResNets’ have also recently been used in the medical domain for lung cancer classification^[31], achieving state-of-the-art accuracy results in the prediction of the majority of

the referral and non-referral nodules. Similarly, in another medical application, WideResNets have been considered for mitosis detection in breast histology images^[32], an approach that ranked the 2nd in the MICCAI TUPAC 2016 competition for mitosis detection. Aditi presented using 3D WideResNets for disease diagnosis, specifically, obtaining better quality denoised brain magnetic resonance images as compared to the state-of-the-art approach^[33].

3 Experimental set-up

In the following the MGFD database will be described, details on the considered feature sets will be given, and the data partitioning and equipment set-up will be indicated.

3.1 MGFD

Figure 1 Interface for the Level 6 of the ‘Crazy Trophy’. Although the user has collected only 10 trophies, due to the (intentional) usability problem, the panel at the right indicates the doubled count, i.e., 20 trophies; this makes it impossible to win the game.

The MGF¹ is a database which contains 5 hours of audiovisual recordings from 67 healthy

1. The MGF dataset is freely accessible in: <https://zenodo.org/record/3957238#.X4A0v3X7TmF>

individuals (27 female, 40 male; with a mean age of 15 years old) experiencing different levels of spontaneous frustration elicited by a variety of (intentional) usability issues. MGF was collected through the users' interaction with the game 'Crazy Trophy', a wizard-of-Oz (WoZ)^[34] voice-controlled game especially designed to induce frustration in the participants. During their interactions with 'CrazyTrophy', the users perceive that the game player, i. e., the avatar, is controlled by their voice (unlike by the WoZ): users were able to use the spoken commands 'left', 'right', 'up', and 'down' to move the avatar. The goal of the game is to collect a specific number of trophies—indicated to the user by a counter (cf. the right panel in Figure 1)—and subsequently deliver them to a bear (cf. the right corner on the top of Figure 1). The target (i. e., the number of trophies to be collected) varies for each of the six game levels, and only one attempt to complete each level is given to the participants, who must finish the task within a specific time in order to win. From level 1–4, since there were no usability problems, the participants generally showed neutral/positive emotions. Differently, in levels 5 and 6, the use of usability problems, e.g., intentionally altering the counter in order to prevent the users from achieving their goals, leads individuals to show different levels of frustration. The baseline provided along with the database presents the results for a binary classification task, i.e., for the discrimination between frustration and no-frustration. Concerning the experimental settings, the authors extracted MFCC acoustic features and applied SVM and LSTM for audio channels. The best baseline result resembles 58.8% of Unweighted Average Recall (UAR) for the considered speech channel.

3.2 Feature sets

A wealth of different feature sets were produced to perform analysis and recognition of speech. Often, in supervised machine learning, performance is compared across different benchmark feature sets, which enables also feature comparison for specific tasks. With this in mind, along with the MFCC features already considered for the baseline, we also evaluate the performance of Mel-Spectrograms and eGeMAPS feature sets, since they have been successfully considered to recognise emotional speech in previous research^{[35], [36]}.

3.2.1 Mel-Spectrograms

Figure 2 Sample Mel-spectrogram extracted from a clip of female frustration speech in seconds

Mel-Spectrograms are generated by applying a Mel filter bank to spectrograms, which are extracted from audio signals via Short Term Fourier Transform (STFT)^[37]. The window length is 2000. We use a hop length of 800. The N-FFT value is 2000. The Mel filter bank converts spectrograms into Mel scales, which was considered since it emphasises the low frequencies over the higher ones, mirroring the human ears' perceptual capability. To compute the Mel-Spectrograms, the 'librosa' python package was used in our experiment. In Figure 2, a sample frustration Mel-Spectrogram is given.

3.2.2 MFCCs

MFCCs are a representation derived by computing the cepstrum of the melodic frequencies^[38]. Due to their high performance^[39], MFCCs are one of the most commonly used filter bank-based feature type for speech processing applications, such as speech recognition^[39], speaker verification/identification^[40], and language identification^[38]. Furthermore, MFCCs offer the advantages of low dimensionality and independence of the position of the partial narrow band corruption across feature dimensions^[41]. In this work, a total of 39-dimensional MFCC features were extracted, including: 13 MFCC coefficients; and the first and second delta regression coefficients (both deltas, i.e., first and second, having 13 dimensions each).

3.2.3 eGeMAPS

The extended Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set (eGeMAPS)^{[42], [43]} is a small (low dimensional) knowledge-based acoustic feature set designed with the purpose of achieving a high level of robustness when capturing emotion from speech^[42]. It consists of a set of 42 low-

level-descriptors (LLDs) and 2 functionals, i.e., the arithmetic mean and the coefficient of variation^[42]. The overall dimensions in eGeMAPS are 88.

3.3 Data partitioning

Table 1: The Dataset Partitioning of Participants and Instances

Models	Train & Dev	Test	Σ
Speakers	45	22	67
Gender(M:F)	30:15	10:12	40:27
Frustration	483	209	692
Non Frustration	3763	1991	5754

Similarly to baseline experimental setting, we applied independent Leave-Three-Speaker-Out Cross Validation method, meaning that the 67 (40 males, 27 females) participants were divided into two subsets. One sub-set was employed as fixed test set (10 males, 12 females); the other (30 males, 15 females) was considered as training and development set in cross validation, being subsequently partitioned into 15 subsets, each including 2 males and 1 female. During the training process, one subset was chosen as development set while the other 14 subsets were utilised as training set; the fixed test set was taken into account to evaluate the model. The distribution of speakers and instances is given in Table 1.

3.4 Equipment set-up

As high performance computing systems are increasingly incorporating the computational power provided by accelerators, especially GPUS. Thus to implement experiments, we applied Nvidia GeForce GTX Titan X as our GPU to increase our computational performance. Our deep learning models were programmed by Pytorch with a MacBook².

4 Deep learning approaches

Current state-of-the-art deep learning methods have explored the use of Residual Networks (ResNets) in different applications, such as earthquake signal detection^[44], infant crying recognition^[45], and pediatric pneumonia diagnosis^[46]. These methods are characterised by the use of particularly deep networks, which makes the model’s training especially time consuming when the depth of ResNets increases, an aspect that might be alleviated by the use of WideResNets^[19] as was outlined above. One of the properties of WideResNets shared with ResNets is the shortcut connections^[31], i. e., the connections that skip one or more layers: they

² For reproducibility, the code to re-implement the experiments is freely accessible in : <https://github.com/Meishu619/frustrationrecognitionfromspeech>

help to reduce the vanishing gradient problem. The main difference between both is the width of the networks.

In this work, the architectures of ResNets and WideResNets are compared with three other typically used CNNs, i. e., AlexNet, VGG, and EfficientNet. The AlexNet^[47] model contains five convolutional layers, two fully connected layers and a softmax output layer. Different from the previous shallow networks, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU), overlap pooling, and dropout are used in this model^[47]. The VGG-11 network consists of eleven weight layers, eight convolutional layers, and three fully connected layers. It classifies by a softmax classifier layer as its output. In addition, the promising EfficientNet^[48], has been presented as a benchmark to balance network depth, width, and resolution. Indeed, although scaling up convolutional neural networks has been widely used to improve networks' accuracy, and it has shown that a simple composite scaling method based on a fixed set of scaling coefficients—thus uniformly scaling the three aforementioned parameters, i.e., depth, width, and resolution. This can be used to efficiently avoid tedious fine-tuning processing^[48].

Figure 3 WideResNets(Blue) and ResNets(Green) model architectures are illustrated.

An overview architecture of the ResNets and WideResNets used in this work can be observed in Figure 3. One of the critical parameters in WideResNets is the widening factor k . It is a coefficient whereby its value will multiply with residual blocks' width to go from ResNets to WideResNets. However, before multiplying with the k factor, the best value cannot be defined deterministic. In this regard, we decide to compare the performance of this architecture using

$k=2$, $k=3$, and $k=4$: in Figure 3, the k factor is set up in residual blocks. Batch normalization^[49] at the output of the convolutional layer is used, and a Rectified Linear Unit(ReLU) function as activation in all the residual blocks is employed. Our network is trained with a batch size of 32 samples. It uses weighted cross-entropy as the loss to be optimised with Adam optimiser. The learning rate considered in our experiments resembles 0.0001. In our architecture, the considered input sizes for the networks are: 1 000 x 39 for MFCCs, 1 000 x 900 for Mel-Spectrograms, and 1 000 x 88 for eGeMAPS.

5 Experimental results

Our classification performance is measured using the Unweited Average Recall(UAR), an evaluation metric already used in previous work on the same dataset^[9] and broadly used in the field, as it is well suited for the typically encountered imbalance of classes. Table 1 presents the results obtained with the considered frustration recognition models, trained using different acoustic feature sets. From the evaluation of the obtained results, we observe that the WideResNets50-2 architecture achieved the best performance using Mel-Spectrogram acoustic features (UAR=93.1 %; cf. test in Table 2), i. e., our best results out performs the baseline in 34.3 %. Similarly, the better result for MFCCs was also achieved with the WideResNets50-2 architecture (UAR=92.9 %; cf. test in Table 2), when considering eGeMAPS as acoustic features, it was the WideResNets50-3 which outperformed the other architectures (UAR=85.7%; cf. test in Table 2). We find that the best k value for Mel-Spectrograms and MFCCs is 2, while for eGeMAPS the optimal k is 3, which indicates that the selection of the k parameter is input-dependent, therefore, it needs to be fine-tuned for the different input features. Note that we do not try further values since we observed that higher k yield to lower performance.

Table 2 Unweighted Average Recall (UAR[%]) results obtained by the evaluated CNN-based models. Three acoustic representations of the input audio signals are considered: MFCCs, eGeMAPS, and Mel-Spectrograms. Results obtained UAR are given; the best results of each feature set are highlighted in bold. Baseline results from previous paper are presented [9].

Models	MFCCs	eGeMAPS	Mel-Spectrograms
Baseline(SVM) ^[9]	58.8	None	None
Baseline(LSTM) ^[9]	57.4	None	None
AlexNet	88.4	82.3	89.2
VGG11	80.1	73.5	80.0
EfficientNet-0	86.1	75.5	87.0
EfficientNet-1	86.2	76.7	89.3
EfficientNet-4	89.2	80.1	90.8
ResNets18	83.7	80.2	88.6
ResNets34	90.0	84.2	89.7
ResNets50	87.3	80.7	91.9
WideResNets50-2	92.9	83.2	93.1
WideResNets50-3	89.3	85.7	91.9
WideResNets50-4	90.8	84.7	90.4

Overall, a comparison with the baseline results^[9] shows that CNN-based architectures yield to a great improvement (from 58.8 % to 93.1 % UAR), which can be observed for all the evaluated CNN models—even the worst result (UAR=73.5%), achieved by the VGG11 architecture using eGeMAPS feature set, outperformed the baseline. We interpret that this might be due to—to some extent—the data collection procedure: In the ‘no-frustration’ clips, individuals pronounced the commands “left”, “right”, “up”, and “down” sequentially, with a high frequency and confidence; differently, in the ‘frustration’ clips, individuals introduced long silences between the commands. We hypothesise that although the MGFDF dataset contains time-sequential data, the numerous silences in the data have biased the performance of the LSTM architecture when modelling frustration in MGFDF. Another interesting outcome is that WideResNets architectures outperform, in most of the cases, the results achieved with ResNets-based models, which confirms that an increase in width, rather than depth, of the residual blocks, leads to a better performance for our speech based frustration detection task. Despite the remarkable performance of EfficientNet in image classification tasks^[48], this kind of architecture obtained lower UAR than the considered ResNets and WideResNets architectures, which might be due to the fact that the resolution for the speech signals in the MGFDF dataset is lower than in the case of image dimensions. Another possible reason is that in EfficientNet,

there are not skip connections.

6 Conclusion

In the presented research, following our work on speech-based frustration recognition during game interaction, we showed that the use of Mel-spectrogram acoustic features with a WideResNets architecture yields to a great improvement (34.3% UAR) w.r.t. the baseline results. Through the comparison across different models, our results confirm that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in general, and the Wide Residual Networks (WideResNets) in particular, are suitable architectures that can successfully retrieve emotional content from speech. Future work will need to re-evaluate this finding on other datasets of frustration and more general paralinguistic tasks to lend additional evidence to the value of WideResNets architectures in the field.

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